

ASSOCIATION OF MOTIVATION AND JOB SATISFACTION WITH WORK ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract

Objective: To establish an association of motivation and job satisfaction with work engagement.

Methods and materials: It is a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in PRTH from May 2025 to July 2025. 150 healthcare professionals including doctors and nurses of both genders were included in this study. Out of these 146 were selected using convenience sampling taken. Data was collected using predesigned online questionnaire which consisted of 5 parts: consent form, demographic details, motivation at work scale, job satisfaction scale and work and well-being survey. Data analysis was done on SPSS version 27 at a 95% confidence level. Multiple chi-square tests were applied to analyze the data, p value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The statistical findings indicated that motivation and job satisfaction were both significantly associated with increased levels of work engagement (p -value 0.001 each) whereas age and gender was not statistically related to work engagement (p -values 0.154 and 0.511 respectively)

Conclusion: It was concluded that both motivation and job satisfaction play a key role in determining an individual's work engagement whereas age and gender do not. Research on this remain scarce in Pakistan highlighting the importance of further research on this topic.

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is a force that originates both internally and externally, compelling individuals to work toward a goal. According to Self-Determination Theory (SDT), motivation can be intrinsic, extrinsic, or a combination of both [1]. An intrinsically motivated individual seeks self-satisfaction and personal achievement [2]. Such individuals work autonomously, focusing on personal growth without expecting external rewards [3]. In contrast, extrinsically motivated individuals pursue tasks to gain rewards or avoid punishments [4]. In healthcare settings, a lack of extrinsic motivation can lead to dissatisfaction,

which increases the likelihood of medical errors and jeopardizes patient safety [5]. Amotivation, defined as the absence of motivation, is associated with feelings of discontent and disengagement in the workplace [6]. It is considered the second most prevalent issue among healthcare workers, following staff shortages [7]. Work engagement is a positive, fulfilling state of mind composed of three essential components: vigor, dedication, and absorption. A vigorous individual demonstrates perseverance and determination in the face of challenges [8]. A dedicated person works enthusiastically and takes pride in their efforts,

while absorption refers to being so engrossed in work that one loses track of time [9]. Job satisfaction is an emotional response—either positive or negative—that influences the quality of healthcare services provided by professionals [10]. Although motivation, job satisfaction, and work engagement have each been studied extensively as individual predictors of employee success, the interaction between motivation and job satisfaction in relation to work engagement remains poorly understood. This study aims to address this gap by examining how motivation and job satisfaction work together to influence work engagement. For this purpose, the following hypotheses were made.

H1= Both impact work engagement positively.

H2= Both impact work engagement negatively.

H3= Both have no impact on work engagement.

H1= Hypothesis One, H2= Hypothesis Two, H3= Hypothesis Three

Keeping in view these hypotheses, the following research question comes to light: Does motivation and job satisfaction affect work engagement?

Materials and methods

Participants

This was a cross-sectional study conducted in PRTH, Lahore during the months May 2025 to July 2025. It incorporated healthcare professionals including a total of 43 nurses, 115 house officers, 12 medical officers and 60 post graduate trainees making a total of 230 healthcare professionals both male and female.

Data Collection

After approval from the ethical review board at PRTH (ERB Ref. No. 75/2025) the data was collected via convenient sampling technique by providing online forms. The sample size was calculated to be 146 according to WHO calculator where confidence interval Z was set at 95%, margin of error ϵ was 5% and total number of participants were 230. A total of 150 forms were filled online to cater for errors that may arise due to incorrect or incomplete filling of forms. The selection criteria were as follows: employees who worked full-time in PRTH including house officers, medical officers, post graduate trainees

and nursing staff, individuals with at least 6 months of work experience in their current role to ensure familiarity with job conditions, participants aged 23 years and above who were willing to provide informed consent. The exclusion criteria included the following: temporary, part-time, or contractual workers as their engagement levels may differ significantly, employees who were on extended leave (e.g., medical or maternity leave) during the data collection period, individuals who did not consent or failed to complete the survey/questionnaire adequately. After the forms were filled out online, the data was uploaded on SPSS version 27 and descriptive analysis was done. Chi-square test was applied and a p value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Questionnaire

The study questionnaire consisted of 5 parts: consent form, demographic details, motivation at work scale, job satisfaction scale and work and well-being survey. The time required to fill in the forms was 8-10 minutes on average. The study tools include:

Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale by Gagné et al.

It uses a 7-point Likert scoring method and has a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.81 [11]. It comprised of 19 questions. According to this scale motivation was further categorized as amotivation, extrinsic regulation including social and material aspects, introjected regulation, identified regulation and intrinsic motivation. Each of these subcategories had 3 questions except for introjected regulation which had 4. Average was calculated for each of these categories separately and then final score was calculated by taking mean of these results. Based on the findings, motivation levels were classified into three categories: **low** for scores ranging from 0 to 2.5, **moderate** for scores between 2.5 and 4.5 and **high** for scores from 4.5 to 7.

Work and Wellbeing Survey by Schaufeli et al.

It uses a 7-point Likert scoring method and has a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.96 [12]. It

consisted of a total of 17 questions. Question 1-6 for vigor, 7-11 for dedication, 12-17 for absorption. Average was calculated for these categories and scoring was done as follows. < 3 = Low vigor, > 3 = High vigor, < 2.5 = Low dedication, > 2.5 = High dedication, < 3 = Low absorption and > 3 = High absorption.

Job Satisfaction Scale by Brayfield and Roth.

This scale had a 5-point Likert scale and a Cronbach alpha of 0.86 [13]. It consisted of 18 questions designed to assess the job satisfaction of healthcare workers. Mean was calculated for each of these questions for all the participants individually and a score for low, moderate and high job satisfaction was assigned as 0-1.7, 1.8-3.5, 3.6-5 respectively.

Results

For the purpose of this study, 150(n=150) healthcare professionals who worked in PRTH were taken into account. This sample included both genders and two subgroups according to age: < 39 years and > 39 years with a predominant younger age group. The relationship of work engagement levels-categorized as low or high- and various factors, including motivation, job satisfaction, gender, and age were determined. For this purpose, chi-square tests were conducted. The analysis revealed a strong statistical association between motivation levels and work engagement. Specifically, among the 22.0%(n=33) highly motivated participants, 75.8%(n=25) reported

high levels of engagement, whereas 78.0%(n=117) of those with low motivation (69 out of 117 participants) reported lower engagement of 41%(n=48)

A similar pattern emerged for job satisfaction, demonstrating a significant relationship with work engagement. Of the 82.7%(n=124) participants who reported high job satisfaction, 56.5%(n=70) indicated high work engagement. In contrast, among the 17.3%(n=26) less satisfied individuals, only 11.5%(n=3) were highly engaged. Gender did not appear to significantly influence work engagement. Out of 49.3%(n=74) of the male healthcare workers only 46%(n=34) were highly engaged in their work. Their female counterparts which compromised 50.7%(n=76) of the sample 51.3%(n=39) were fully engaged in their work. Thus, there was no notable difference in engagement levels between male and female participants, with numbers being largely consistent across genders(p-value 0.511)Conversely, age did show a substantial impact on engagement; particularly engagement levels of individuals aged > 39 years were significantly more than younger individuals given as 80%(n=4) and 47.6%(n=69) Despite these differences in numbers age did not affect work engagement statistically(p-value 0.154).In summary, while motivation and job satisfaction were found to influence work engagement, gender and age did not demonstrate a strong correlation.

Table 1 . Work Engagement and Its Relation with Different Variables

Major Category	Subcategory	n (%)	Low Work Engagement n = 77 (51.3%)	High Work Engagement n = 73 (48.7%)	p-value
Motivation	Low	117 (78.0)	69 (59.0)	48 (41.0)	
	High	33 (22.0)	8 (24.2)	25 (75.8)	0.001*
Job Satisfaction	Low	26 (17.3)	23 (88.5)	3 (11.5)	0.001*
	High	124 (82.7)	54 (43.5)	70 (56.5)	

Major Category	Subcategory	n (%)	Low Work Engagement n = 77 (51.3%)	High Work Engagement n = 73 (48.7%)	p-value
Gender	Male	74 (49.3)	40 (54.0)	34 (46.0)	0.511*
	Female	76 (50.7)	37 (48.7)	39 (51.3)	
Age (years)	< 39	145 (96.7)	76 (52.4)	69 (47.6)	0.154*
	≥ 39	5 (3.3)	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)	

*Chi-square test was used for comparison. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Figure 1 : Frequency distribution for work engagement.

Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to examine the association between **motivation**, **job satisfaction**, and **work engagement** among healthcare professionals. The findings revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between both motivation and job satisfaction with work engagement ($p = .001$ for each). These results offer a foundation for designing targeted interventions that enhance employee engagement through a multifaceted strategy.

To improve work engagement, organizations should address both **intrinsic** and **extrinsic** motivational factors. Intrinsic motivators—such as a sense of purpose, autonomy, and opportunities

for professional growth—play a critical role in fostering engagement. Simultaneously, extrinsic factors like recognition, fair compensation, and clear career advancement pathways must be adequately supported.

Previous research supported these findings. For instance, intrinsic motivation had been identified as a personal resource that positively influenced work engagement [14]. Similar studies had emphasized the role of financial rewards in enhancing engagement alongside intrinsic drivers [15]. Moreover, both types of motivation contribute to job satisfaction, which in turn improved performance and engagement [16]. Autonomy in decision-making had also been shown to increase job satisfaction and work

engagement [17]. Occupational gratification has similarly been linked to higher levels of engagement [18].

Interestingly, this study did not find a statistically significant relationship between **age** or **gender** and work engagement. This aligns with the limited global research exploring these demographic variables as determinants of engagement.

Despite its contributions, the study has several limitations. First, the sample lacked professional diversity, focusing solely on healthcare professionals, which limits the generalizability of the findings to other sectors. Second, the research was conducted within a single private institution, making it difficult to extrapolate results to public sector organizations. Third, the relatively small sample size may affect the reliability of the findings when applied to larger populations.

Future research should aim to include a more diverse sample across various professions and organizational settings to enhance the generalizability of findings. Additionally, demographic variables such as age and gender warrant deeper exploration to uncover potential moderating effects. To strengthen the validity of current conclusions, subsequent studies should employ larger and more representative samples.

Conclusions

This study aimed to explore the relationship of motivation and job satisfaction with work engagement. The results demonstrated a statistically significant positive correlation between work engagement and both motivation and job satisfaction, identifying these variables as independent predictors of engagement.

The outcomes of this research offer meaningful guidance for healthcare organizations seeking to strengthen employee engagement. To strengthen the validity of current conclusions, subsequent studies should employ larger and more representative samples. By fostering intrinsic motivators—such as autonomy, purpose, and professional development—and ensuring extrinsic factors like recognition, fair compensation, and career progression are addressed, institutions can promote a more engaged, satisfied, and productive workforce.

Conflict of interest

None to declare.

Participants consent

The consent of the healthcare professionals was taken prior to writing this manuscript.

Authors contribution

The following authors made significant contributions to this manuscript.

- Dr. Muhammad Farooq
- Dr Bisma Javed
- Dr Syed Muhammad Talha
- Mujtaba Ahmad
- Dr Zainab Nadeem

All authors take full responsibility for this manuscript and commit to addressing any issues related to its accuracy and integrity through proper investigation and resolution.

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